

Introduction of Arsenic into Coumarin Nucleus.

Part II.

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It has already been pointed out in our previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 417) that the groups $\text{O}-\text{CO}$ and $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ present in coumarin nucleus together with arsenic might prove to have some effect in the treatment of tuberculosis. The present paper deals with certain new substituted coumarins and naphthacoumarins containing the same therapeutically active components in the nucleus. The following compounds are described in the present paper: 7-methylcoumarin-5-arsinic acid (I), 4:7-dimethylcoumarin-6-arsinic acid (II), 1:2- α -naphthapyrone-6-arsinic acid (III) and 4-methyl-1:2- α -naphthapyrone-6-arsinic acid (IV).

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

These have been prepared from their amino derivatives by Bart's reaction and unlike the arsenic derivative of coumarin (*loc. cit.*),

they all gave monoderivatives. Attempts to introduce arsenic into 8-amino-4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin and 8-amino-4-methyl-7-methoxycoumarin were not successful.

It appears that no attempt has yet been made to nitrate 1:2-a-naphthapyrone. The compound was nitrated by a mixture of fuming nitric acid and acetic acids. The position at which the nitro group entered the nucleus was supposed to be "6" from an analogy of the other nitro derivatives of coumarin.

The arsenic compounds described are generally light yellow in colour and dissolve very easily in caustic alkalis and alkali carbonates from which hydrochloric acid precipitates the original compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL.

7-Methylcoumarin-6-arsinic acid.—7-Methyl-6-aminocoumarin (4 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of hot water (80 c.c.) and hydrochloric acid (6 c.c.) and the mixture was heated to boiling and then suddenly cooled to 0°, the object being to obtain the sparingly soluble hydrochloride in a fine state of division. The amino compound was then diazotised in the usual manner using a solution of sodium nitrite (2 g.) in water (10 c.c.) and the diazo solution gradually added to well cooled alkaline solution of sodium arsenite prepared from sodium carbonate (8 g.) arsenious acid (3 g.) water (100 c.c.) and copper sulphate (16 g.) as catalyst, and the whole mass was kept well stirred during the operation. The stirring was continued for one hour more after the addition of the diazo solution. The separated tarry and insoluble matters were filtered off. The filtrate concentrated to a low bulk, boiled with animal charcoal and filtered hot. It was then cooled to the room temperature and concentrated hydrochloric acid was gradually added till the precipitated compound dissolved in excess of the strong acid in which it is soluble. At this stage the solution was again filtered from the tarry and insoluble matters, the filtrate rendered alkaline and the arsenic compound was precipitated with careful addition of dilute hydrochloric acid as yellowish white stuff. The repetition of the above process gave the compound in a sufficiently pure condition, m.p. 290° (decomp.). (Found: As, 26.0. $C_{10}H_9O_5As$ requires As, 26.4 per cent.).

4:7-Dimethyl-6-arsinic acid.—*4:7-Dimethyl-6-aminocoumarin* (2.2 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of hydrochloric acid (2.5 g.) and water (20 c.c.) and diazotised in the same manner as stated above with a solution of sodium nitrite (9 g.) in water (10 c.c.). This was gradually added to a well stirred sodium arsenite solution made of sodium carbonate (4 g.), arsenious oxide (1.5 g.), copper sulphate (.07 g.) and water (60 c.c.). The resulting product was filtered, concentrated, boiled with animal charcoal and again filtered. The filtrate was cooled and then gradually acidified with hydrochloric acid when cream coloured precipitate of arsenic derivative was obtained. The precipitate was separated by filtration, purified as in the previous case, washed with hot water and then dried in a vacuum desiccator; m.p. 285° (decomp.). (Found: As, 24.8. $C_{11}H_{11}O_5As$ requires As, 25.3 per cent.).

6-Nitro-1:2- α -naphthapyrone.—*1:2- α -Naphthapyrone* (48 g.) was dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.). To this hot solution, nitric acid (15 c.c. *d* 1.52) was gradually added. The whole was then heated on the water-bath with constant stirring and the heating continued till the crystals of the nitro compound appeared. At this stage the product was poured upon pounded ice when dark yellow nitro derivative separated. This was filtered, washed free from acid and crystallised from acetone in yellow microcrystalline powder, m.p. 180°, yield theoretical. (Found: N, 5.75. $C_{13}H_7O_4N$ requires N, 5.8 per cent.).

6-Amino-1:2- α -naphthapyrone.—*6-Nitronaphthacoumarin* (24 g.) was gradually added to a warm clear solution of stannous chloride (70 g.) in a mixture of hydrochloric acid (60 c.c.) and alcohol (50 c.c.). The reduction was over when every thing went into solution. More hydrochloric acid (120 c.c.) was now added and the solution allowed to cool when the hydrochloride of the base separated out. It was filtered, washed thoroughly with concentrated hydrochloric acid, dissolved in hot water and treated with a hot solution of sodium acetate when the base was liberated as golden yellow crystals, m.p. 194°, yield 60 per cent.

α -Naphthapyrone-6-arsinic acid.—This was prepared from *6-amino-1:2- α -naphthapyrone* as above. It was obtained as yellow microcrystalline powder from alcohol not melting even upto 360°. The yield was very low. (Found: As, 22.9. $C_{13}H_9O_5As$ requires As 23.4 per cent.).

4-Methyl-1:2-a-naphthapyrone-6-arsinic acid.—It was prepared from 6-amino-4-methyl-1:2-a-naphthapyrone and purified in a similar way and crystallised from acetic acid as a yellowish white microcrystalline powder. The acid shrinks at 340° but does not melt even at 360°. (Found: As 22·3. $C_{14}H_{11}O_5As$ requires As 22·4 per cent.).

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